

STRESS AND MENTAL HEALTH ITS EFFECT ON JOB SATISFACTION: BASIS FOR DEVELOPMENTAL PROGRAM

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Stress and Mental Health its Effect on Job Satisfaction: Basis for Developmental Program

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Abstract

The study attempted to assess the level of stress of public-school teachers in the West I District, taking into consideration their demographic profile as well as the factors influencing it. Furthermore, it intends to know the relationship between their mental health status and job satisfaction. This study utilized the descriptive- correlational research design with 132 randomly selected teachers under West I District as the respondents of the study. Frequency distribution and percentage were utilized to get the profile of the respondents. To obtain the significant relationship between variables the Pearson Product Moment correlation, ANOVA and Regression were used. Results showed that there is no significant relationship between the level of occupational stress and the mental health of the respondents when grouped according to their profile. The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the respondents' socio-demographic profile and their occupational stress show that there is a positive relationship in terms of age and highest educational attainment. There is no significant relationship between the level of occupational stress and mental health and the job satisfaction of the respondents. Results showed that all of the mentioned socio-demographic profiles are not predictors of their job satisfaction as indicated in their p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance. Regardless of differences in these socio- demographic characteristics among individuals, they do not seem to have a notable impact on how satisfied they are with their work.

Keywords: *stress, occupational stress, mental health, job satisfaction, socio-demographic profile*

Introduction

Teachers and job satisfaction were often found to have different operating circumstances and experience higher levels of work-related stress than usual and typical organizations' employees (Abaasi 2016). Teachers have multiple responsibilities as they are required to educate students, ensure their safety and a healthy atmosphere, communicate and jointly work together with parents, specialists, and administrators, and knowledge, administer documents, organize school trips, and complete a range of other tasks like co-curricular activities provided by the government and school administration.

Republic Act No. 11036, an Act Establishing a National Mental Health Policy for the Purpose of Enhancing the Delivery of Integrated Mental Health Services, Promoting and Protecting the Rights of Persons Utilizing Psychosocial Health Services, Appropriating Funds Therefor and Other Purposes known as "Mental Health Act.". The state affirms the basic right of all Filipinos to mental health as well as the fundamental rights of people who require mental health services. The state commits itself to promoting the well-being of people by ensuring that; mental health is valued, promoted and protected; mental health conditions are treated and prevented; timely, affordable, high quality, and culturally-appropriate mental health care is made available to the public; mental health services are free from coercion and accountable to the service users; and persons affected by mental health conditions are able to exercise the full range of human rights, and participate fully in society and at work free from stigmatization and discrimination. Sec. 4, Definitions, j, mental health refers to a state of well-being in which the individual realizes one's own abilities and potentials, copes adequately with the normal stresses of life, displays resilience in the face of extreme life events, works productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a positive contribution to the community. While Sec. 4 Definitions, k, mental health condition refers to a neurologic or psychiatric condition characterized by the existence of a recognizable, clinically-significant disturbance in an individual's cognition, emotional regulation, or behavioral that reflects a genetic or acquired dysfunction in the neurological, psychosocial, or developmental process underlying mental functioning.

In line with this, the Department of Education issued a memorandum No. 093 series of 2022, enjoying all offices and schools to join the observance of the 2022 National Mental Health Month. By joining the observance, DepEd brings together stakeholders and enjoins them to take part in ensuring the mental health and well-being of all personnel, learners, and others concerned both in schools and physical workspaces and online (DepEd, 2022).

The mental health and stress level of teachers are two important factors that allow them to become holistic classroom managers and leaders. Teachers are the front lines of the Department of Education (DepEd) in delivering its curriculum, services, and skills mastery to the learners. During the pandemic, although schools are not yet ready to implement distance learning (Asio and Bayucca, 2021), the delivery of learning must go on. Teachers attend training and workshops and undergo technical assistance from mentors and experts to be well-equipped for school-related activities, become prepared for teaching, and evolve into holistic developers of the learners. According to former DepEd Secretary Leonor Briones, not only the teachers are suffering from a heavy workload, but everyone in government service is overworked and under immense pressure (Terrazola, 2018).

This further proves that public school teachers are bombarded with work- related assignments such as reports, instructional materials, school designations, and other related tasks apart from their usual six-hour teaching load every day. This work situation leads to the

dwindling performance of teachers from its target, which is beyond the Proficiency Level. Given this workload, actual teaching tasks are being sidelined by the multitude of other responsibilities and roles teachers play (David et al., 2019). With a bulk of work left undone (e.g. last quarter exam, computation of grades, issuance of cards, reading of forms, etc.) in the outgoing school year, teachers are awaiting the directive to process under the new normal of the education agency. This “new normal” prepares the teachers to be equipped with adaptive leadership and increased technological competence, which are primary and valuable skills to master. This situation brought worries, fears, and uncertainties among teachers, which steered them to apply abroad and work in another department or field.

Occupational stress is the harmful physical and emotional responses that can happen when there is a conflict between job demands on the employee and the amount of control an employee has over meeting these demands (Mental Health Association, 2018). In general, the combination of high demands in a job and low control over the situation can lead to stress.

Nowadays, stress has become an important part of every sector. Most people in this world experience stress and many people can roughly understand stress in the workplace can have many origins or come from one single event. It can affect both employees and employers alike. It is generally believed that some stress is okay, sometimes referred to as "challenge" or "positive stress" but when stress occurs in amounts that others cannot handle and has a direct bearing on mental health.

Mental health is part of the wider notion of health and everyday living. Mental health can affect daily life, relationships, and even physical health. Generally, Mental health is recognized to be an economic and societal burden nationally and globally (Jenkins et al. 2002). However, when nurtured and practiced it becomes an indicator of a successful performance of mental function, resulting in productive activities, fulfilling relationships with other people, and providing the ability to adapt to change and cope with adversity.

Moreover, job satisfaction is a measure of workers' contentedness with their jobs, whether or not they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as the nature of work or supervision. Significantly, job satisfaction and motivation are essential to the continuing growth of educational systems around the world and they rank alongside professional knowledge and skills, center competencies, educational resources as well as strategies, in genuinely determining educational success and performance. However, the problem concerning the job performance of the teachers always refers to the teachers of negligence, laziness, purposeful lethargy, and lack of dedication and zeal to work. They further argue that teachers' level of efficiency and effectiveness does not necessitate the constant request for salary increases, incentives, and better working conditions. Teachers on their part argue that the existing salary structure, benefits, and working conditions do not satisfy their basic needs in as much as other sectors of the economy have bigger salary structures, better motivation, and enhanced working conditions (Ololube, 2006).

In this connection, this study is conducted to assess the level of occupational stress and mental health and its effect on job satisfaction among the school teachers of West I District during the school year 2023-2024 the findings of the study would serve as the basis for Professional Development Program.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine occupational stress and mental health and its effect on job satisfaction. Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. average family monthly income?
2. What is the level of occupational stress and mental health of the respondents?
3. What is the level of job satisfaction of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of occupational stress and mental health of the respondents when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of occupational stress and mental health and the job satisfaction of the respondents?
6. Which of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents best predict their level of job satisfaction?
7. What development program can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher employed the descriptive-correlational research design to collect and analyze data on at least two variables to see if there is a link between them. The descriptive survey method was used, wherein the acquisition of information was taken from every member of the teacher respondents' population by answering questions that best describe the relationship between the respondent's

demographic profile, occupational stress, and mental health and its effect on job satisfaction.

The data interpretation of the respondents' profiles, utilizes a quantitative approach to process the information gathered from the questionnaires. This information was analyzed in terms of its content and relevance to the problems stated in this study. To determine the extent relationship of the respondent's profile to their occupational stress, mental health, and its effect on job satisfaction. To determine also what professional development program could be crafted based on the findings of the study.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the faculty and staff of West I District, Division of Iligan City. A total population of 132 was selected as participants of the study through raosoft calculator. The researcher employs random sampling to generate the sample population of learners using the Raosoft sampling to determine the number of participants.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Name of Schools</i>	<i>No. of Teachers</i>	<i>Random No. of Respondents</i>
Estenzo Comendador Memorial Elementary School	9	7
Suarez Central School	70	53
Tomas Cabili Integrated School	38	29
Bernardo E. Ramos Memorial School	8	6
Angelico Medina Memorial Elementary School	34	26
Victor G. Guevara Memorial School	15	11
Total	170	132

Instrument

This study utilized adopted questionnaire instruments to obtain data from the respondents. The first part is the self-made questionnaire that deals with the demographic profile of the respondents. It is used to gather the background information of the profile includes the age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, average family income and position. The second part is the questionnaire about occupational stress by Hart (1985), mental health using The Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10), and the Job satisfaction survey by Spector (1994).

Occupational Stress Scaling:

The Stress Assessment Questionnaire is a 20-item test based on the book Adrenalin and Stress by Archibald Hart (1985) and modified into 15 items using a scale of 1; I have never experienced this symptom, 2; I suffer from it sometimes (about once per month), 3; I have suffered from it more than once per month but not more than once a week, and 4; I often suffer from it (more than once per week).

Job Satisfaction Scaling

The Job satisfaction survey (JSS) is a questionnaire used to evaluate nine dimensions of job satisfaction related to overall satisfaction. This instrument is well established among the other job satisfaction scales. The test is composed of 15 items or 4 items for each of the nine sub-scales. For each item, there are choices between "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" 4 choices in all, with which the participants must respond. The Job Satisfaction Survey or JSS has some of its items written in each direction-positive and negative. Scores on each of the nine facet subscales, based on 4 items each, while scores for total job satisfaction, based on the sum of all 15 items. Each item is scored from 1 to 4 if the original response choices are used. High scores on the scale represent job satisfaction, so the scores on the negatively worded items must be reversed before summing with the positively worded into facet or total scores. A score of 4 representing the strongest agreement with a negatively worded item is considered equivalent to a score of 1 representing the strongest disagreement on a positively worded item, allowing them to be combined meaningfully.

Mental Health - Depression Anxiety Stress Scaling:

Depression, Anxiety, and Stress (DASS) is a questionnaire where depression, anxiety, and stress are all negative feelings that may turn to mental health. The DASS has 40 items and modified into 15 items.

Procedure

Before commencing the study, an official letter was sent to the Department of Education in the Division of Iligan City. This letter contained a formal request addressed to the respective school heads, accompanied by a signed letter from the Schools Division Superintendent. This step not only established the study's legitimacy but also demonstrated respect for institutional protocols and guidelines. This initiation phase is estimated to occur between December 2023 and March 2024.

During the study's execution, participants were presented with a consent form, providing them with comprehensive information about the study's objectives, anticipated timeline, methodologies, and their entitlement to decline participation or withdraw at any stage. Ethical standards were strictly upheld throughout the research process. This transparent approach fostered trust and encouraged honest

and uninhibited participation.

Upon distribution of the various questionnaires, participants were instructed accordingly. To ensure that responses are accurate, participants are invited to seek clarification or ask questions as they complete the questionnaires. The researcher actively interacted with participants while distributing the surveys, creating a cooperative and encouraging environment that encouraged candid discussion and the development of trust. This method improved the quality and dependability of the data gathered by fostering a relationship and encouraging open communication. The questionnaires were delivered during the faculty's Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions, ensuring ample time for completion, with careful consideration for the respondents' comfort, preferred time frames, and overall well-being. This phase was projected to take place from February to March 2024.

Following the retrieval of completed questionnaires, a meticulous process of checking, tallying, and consolidation was conducted to organize the gathered data. This phase is expected to occur between February and March 2024. Overall, the data collection approach was marked by adherence to ethical principles, methodological rigor, and attention to the research context's particular qualities and needs. The study aimed to provide relevant and practical insights that may impact educational policy and practice in schools by incorporating these factors at each level of the research process.

Data Analysis

To ensure the reliability of the results of the research data, the researcher organized and documented the data based on what was measured quantitatively. The data gathered for the study will be analyzed and interpreted using the following tools:

Problem 1, Frequency and percentage distribution. This was used to describe the profile distribution of the respondents.

Problem 2 and 3, Weighted mean and standard deviation. It was used to determine the level of workplace stress, mental health status, and job satisfaction of the respondents.

Problem 4 and 5, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Chi-square. It was used to determine the significant difference in the workplace stress, mental health, and job satisfaction of the respondents when grouped according to their profile. And determine the relationship between job satisfaction and mental health, and the workplace stress level of the respondents.

Problem 6, Multiple Regression analysis with a simultaneous entry was utilized to test if the predictors significantly affected occupational stress and mental health to job satisfaction of respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the data that are shown in the tables. The data were analyzed, interpreted, and supported by related literature or studies.

Problem 1: What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average monthly income?

Table 2. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age Bracket (yrs. Old)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
25-34	28	21.00
35-44	45	34.00
45-54	43	33.00
55 and above	16	12.00
Total	132	100.00

Ages of respondents are portrayed in Table 2. It indicated that maximum number of them was 35-44 years old who were 45, that accounted for 34% out of the total number of respondents which was around 132, followed by the age group of 45-54 years which is represented by 43, or rather a third. Only few people could be found to fall within the age group of above 55; this only amounted to about 16 or alternatively 12%. These ages correspond to Erikson's psychosocial stages middle adulthood period between ages 35 and 45. Ages from twenty five through thirty four comprise twenty one percent (21%) which equals to twenty eight (28) among them as shown in table no.2 below. It can be deduced from this information that newly recruited teachers have an average age range between twenty-two and thirty-five years with most being novice teachers having served for just two years on average.

In contrast, the age range of 55 years and beyond had the fewest respondents, with only 16 individuals (12%) falling into this category. This data suggests that older individuals, potentially approaching retirement age, are underrepresented in the sample. Ages 55 and above have 16 out of 132 or 12% for this is a retireable age of teachers.

In the Philippines, the retirement age for teachers, particularly those in the public sector, is generally set at 60 years old. However, there are provisions that allow for earlier retirement under certain conditions. These conditions can vary depending on the specific rules and regulations set by educational institutions or government agencies. House Bill No. 206 is a consolidation of 13 related measures. It is entitled, "An Act lowering the optional retirement age of government workers from sixty years to 56 years, amending for the purpose

Section 13-A of Republic Act 8291, otherwise known as The Government Service Insurance System Act of 1997.” The amendment to Section 13 (Retirement Benefits) subparagraph (b) of RA 8291. One common provision for early retirement among teachers is the optional retirement program. Under this program, teachers who have reached a certain age, often around 55 years old, and have served a minimum number of years in the education system may opt to retire early and receive retirement benefits.

Furthermore, the analysis focuses on the age group 25-34 years old, which accounted for 28 respondents (21%). This age group is most likely made up of younger educators who are still in the early to mid-stages of their professions. Given their decreased representation compared to middle-aged groups, it appears that the sample is skewed towards more experienced educators.

The interpretation of these data in the context of Erikson's Psychosocial phases deepens the analysis, particularly in terms of comprehending the developmental phases and obstacles experienced by people of different ages. The emphasis on middle age coincides with Erikson's concept of generativity against stagnation, as people in this stage are often concerned with contributing to society and leaving a legacy.

Moreover, the fact that a large proportion of respondents are relatively new to teaching, with the majority having been in the profession for two years or less, provides useful background. This shows that the teaching workforce may be facing turnover or an inflow of new educators, which could affect organizational dynamics, professional development activities, and institutional knowledge transmission.

Table 3. *Respondents' Sex*

<i>Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	12	9.00
Female	120	91.00
Total	132	100.00

Table 3 shows the respondents' profile in terms of sex. It can be gleaned that the majority of the respondents were females which is 120 out of 132 or 91%, while 9% or 12 of the respondents were males. This result showed that the teaching profession was dominated by female teachers in terms of the highest number in the study.

These results emphasize the substantial number of female educators in the teaching profession, as indicated by the sample's substantially higher representation of women versus men. The fact that female teachers outweigh male teachers is consistent with broader trends described in education research, which show that women have historically been overrepresented in the teaching workforce in a variety of settings and countries.

Traditionally, teaching has been considered a suitable profession for women, particularly in early childhood education. In the past, societal norms often dictated that women should take on nurturing roles, which aligned with teaching. Female teacher's way of teaching is widely believed that female students benefit from particularly when these teachers serve as counter-stereotypical role models (Card, et al., 2022). Similarly, Oco (2022) indicated that teaching profession is still dominated by females.

Historically, teaching has been connected with nurturing and caring roles, which are consistent with traditional gender norms that assign domestic and caring responsibilities to women. These entrenched preconceptions may deter men from pursuing jobs in education, as teaching may be regarded as incompatible with traditional ideals of masculinity. Furthermore, cultural biases and gendered conceptions of specific subjects or grade levels may drive men away from teaching positions usually held by women, such as early childhood or primary school.

The report of Civil Service Commission (CSC) as quoted by Congressional Commission on Education (CCE) reported in 1991, eighty-four-point two (84.2) percent of the teachers' population was occupied by females. Even the Department of Education record showed that 86% of its employees were women, several studies also revealed that female populace dominated the teaching world.

Table 4. *Respondents' Civil Status*

<i>Civil Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Single Married	20	15.00
Single Parent	106	80.00
	6	5.00
Total	132	100.00

Table 4 presented the profile of the respondents in terms of their civil status. Majority are married which is 106 out of 132 or 80%. The least number of teacher respondents are those who are single parents which is only 5% or 6 in all, while there were 20 or 15% who are still single.

However, the small number of respondents who were single parents (about 5% of the sample as a whole) may highlight the unique challenges that come with juggling the demands of single parenthood with teaching responsibilities. This minority of single parents in the teaching profession should be given special consideration when designing policies that support their unique requirements and advance their professional welfare, as well as when allocating resources and offering support services.

In addition, the 15% of responders who are single teachers represent a diverse range of personal circumstances and life phases within the teaching profession. The values, goals, and support systems of single people may differ from those of married people, which emphasizes the value of acknowledging and valuing a range of viewpoints and experiences in the workplace.

Many people see the pyramid-shaped Abraham Maslow Hierarchy of Needs, with the most fundamental requirements at the base and the most complicated demands at the top. Maslow's hierarchy of needs places the need for love and belonging at level three, which encompasses strong friendships, family relationships, and interpersonal interactions. The need for love and belonging comes before the needs for security and health, as well as before self-actualization and self-esteem. This suggests that the pursuit of more lofty goals like self-actualization and personal development may be subordinated to the development of strong relationships and a sense of community.

Overall, marriage can be viewed as a means of satisfying the need for belongingness and love as outlined in Maslow's hierarchy, providing individuals with a sense of connection, intimacy, and support within a committed relationship.

These findings have implications for workplace policies, professional development programs, corporate culture, and workplace dynamics in higher education that go beyond demographics. The design of specific interventions, such as flexible work schedules, family-friendly policies, and support networks, can be informed by an understanding of the different requirements and situations that teachers face depending on their civil status. These interventions are intended to improve teacher well-being, retention, and job satisfaction.

Table 5. Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Baccalaureate Degree	18	13.00
With Masteral Units	67	51.00
Masters Degree	38	29.00
With Doctoral Units	5	4.00
Doctorate Degree	4	3.00
Total	132	100.00

The presentation of Table 5, showed that the majority, or 51% which is 67 out of 132 of the respondents are those teachers that acquired Masteral Units, while the least number is the teachers who completed the Doctorate Degree which is only 3% or 4 teacher respondents only.

Teachers seek Master's degrees for a variety of reasons, including as chances for specialization, job progression, enhanced expertise in their industry, and personal and professional growth. Teachers holding advanced degrees may have easier access to professional development opportunities such as conferences, seminars, and workshops. An advanced degree may provide doors to career advancement as a department head, curriculum coordinator, or administrator, among other roles.

In consonance with DepEd Order No. 66 s. 2007 "Revised Guidelines on the Appointment and Promotion of Other Teaching, Related Teaching and Non- Teaching Positions", ranking for vacancies to Teacher II and Teacher III positions for Elementary Level will be conducted at the Division Office and for the Secondary Level and Implementing Units. Teachers can be promoted if they meet the requirements for the position they're applying for. They have to get excellent performance ratings and submit documents like training certification, personal data sheet, transcript, and updated service record. The Department of Education uses a point system as criteria for promotion. Moreover, a division review committee is in charge of evaluating teachers for possible advancement.

However, obtaining a doctorate requires extensive study—three to five years of full-time study, on average. Many teachers may find it challenging to balance their doctoral studies with their teaching responsibilities, personal obligations, and other commitments. Since doctoral programs can be costly, many teachers—especially those who are already providing for their families or themselves through their teaching salary—may be reluctant to take on additional debt from student loans or financial burdens. In addition, compared to other graduate schools, doctorate stipends or funding options could be less accessible. Additionally, doctoral stipends or funding opportunities may be limited compared to other graduate programs.

Likewise, not all teachers aspire to pursue leadership roles or research-oriented careers that typically require a doctorate. Some teachers may be satisfied with their current positions and feel that a doctoral degree is not necessary for their career advancement or personal fulfillment.

Table 6. Respondents' Average Monthly Income

<i>Average Monthly Income</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
P20,000-25,000	20	15.00
P 26,000-30,000	66	50.00
P 31,000-35,000	26	20.00
P36,000-40,000	4	3.00
P41,000-45,000	3	2.00
P46,000-50,000	7	5.00
P51,000 and above	6	5.00
Total	132	100.00

The presentation of Table 6, shows that the majority, or 50% which is 66 out of 132 of the respondents are those teachers who have an average monthly income, while the least number of teachers have an average monthly income of 41,000-45,000 which is only 2% of teacher respondents only. This distribution indicates that the majority of respondents have monthly incomes within the lower to middle range, suggesting that while teaching may provide stable employment, higher income brackets are less common among the surveyed teachers.

In many public-school systems, teacher salaries are determined by salary schedules or scales based on factors such as education level and years of experience. These salary schedules may result in relatively low starting salaries for new teachers, with incremental increases as they gain experience and education. Many teachers begin their careers in entry-level roles that pay less. Teachers who are newly qualified or have little experience may start out at the bottom of the pay range.

The basic salaries of Filipino teachers range from Php 27,439 to Php 38,150, depending on their position and the salary grade teacher table. In the case of public schools, brand new teachers start as Teacher I on salary grade 11 then slowly work their way up. The same goes for teachers with specializations. Starting at salary grade 14, special science teachers will be paid at grade 13, head teachers will be paid at grade 14, and master teachers will be paid at grade 18.

Beginner principals, being of a higher rank, have a higher pay grade. Assistant principal 1 is at salary grade 18 and principal 1 starts at salary grade 19. Those in administrative positions, like district supervisors have a pay grade of 22.

Public school teachers typically earn more than their private school counterparts because of the 2019 Salary Standardization Law. Salary levels at public schools are predicted to be 65-87% higher than those in the private sector between 2021 and 2024. Under Republic Act No. 1146, there will be further salary increases for government employees depending on position and current pay grade in 2023. Of course, there will be a salary increase for teachers this 2024. (Written by: Alyssa Divina | Reviewed by: Digidio Financial Writers Team)

Moreover, teachers with advanced degrees, such as master's degrees, specialist degrees, or doctoral degrees, tend to earn higher salaries. However, not all teachers pursue additional education beyond a bachelor's degree. Those who do may command higher salaries due to their increased qualifications and expertise. These findings hold implications for salary structures, compensation guidelines, and economic inequality in the teaching profession, in addition to more general financial considerations. Reducing economic inequality among educators is essential to fostering stability in finances, contentment in the workplace, and career retention. Furthermore, fair compensation policies are essential for drawing and keeping gifted people in the teaching field, especially in light of the growing concerns surrounding teacher shortages and recruitment difficulties.

Problem 2: What is the level of occupational stress and mental health of the respondents?

Table 7. Respondents' Level of Occupational Stress

<i>Occupational Stress Item</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
OS1. Do you often have headaches?	2.27	Sometimes
OS2. Do you suffer from tension or stiffness in the neck, shoulders, jaw, arms, hands, legs or stomach?	2.14	Sometimes
OS3. Do you feel your heart beating strong or faster than usual sometimes?	2.02	Sometimes
OS4. Do you sometimes have difficulty breathing?	1.68	Sometimes
OS5. Do you suffer sometimes from dizziness or light-headedness?	2.03	Sometimes
OS6. Do you often suffer from flu, hoarseness?	2.03	Sometimes
OS7. Do you often suffer from indigestion, nausea, stomach ache?	1.86	Sometimes
OS8. Do you bite your nails?	1.28	Never
OS9. Do you have difficulties falling sleep, or sleeping for a whole night?	2.08	Sometimes
OS10. Do you feel tired in the morning?	2.12	Sometimes
OS11. Do you have your hands or feet cold?	1.65	Sometimes
OS12. Do your teeth tend to gnash? Do your jaws hurt?	1.43	Never
OS13. Do you tend to sweat a lot?	1.92	Sometimes
OS14. Are you irritable or easily got angry?	2.15	Sometimes
OS15. Do you think you might be suffering from anxiety, worry, agitation, nervousness?	2.01	Sometimes
<i>Average</i>	<i>1.91</i>	<i>Sometimes</i>

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never Experience; 1.50-2.49, Experience Sometimes; 2.50-3.49, Experience once a week or in a month; 3.50-4.00, Experience more than once a week.

Table 7 displays the occupational stress of the respondents it revealed that they sometimes experienced feelings of anxiety, worry, agitation, and nervousness. Likewise, they sometimes have difficulties sleeping and never had experience in biting their nails, teeth gnashing, or jaws hurting. These findings suggest that while some stress symptoms are experienced occasionally, others are not as common among the respondents. It gives important information on the mental and emotional health of the educators in the study sample by outlining the occupational stress that the respondents faced. The revelation that respondents occasionally experience feelings of anxiety, concern, agitation, and uneasiness implies that a considerable proportion of teachers suffer from psychological discomfort as

a result of their professional jobs.

The fact that certain participants occasionally have trouble falling asleep emphasizes even more how much occupational stress affects teachers' general well-being. Sleep disorders may exacerbate the negative impacts of occupational stress and lead to burnout and weariness in educators by negatively affecting physical health, cognitive function, and job performance.

On the other hand, the lack of experiences with biting nails, gnashing teeth, or jaw pain could suggest that specific stress-related behaviors are not as common in the study sample. However, it's important to understand that everyone experiences stress in various ways and that psychological discomfort or work-related stress might still exist even in the absence of obvious physical signs.

The implications of these findings include teacher support, professional development, and organizational initiatives aimed at reducing occupational stress and enhancing teacher well-being. Strategies such as giving access to mental health services, stress management courses, and creating supportive school settings can help educators cope with occupational stress and build resilience.

Moderate or optimum level of stress is considered desirable or productive instead of high stress level which hampers the physical as well as mental health of the person. In fact, one actually needs moderate levels of stress to help stay alert and perform well. Moderate levels of stress may motivate an individual or improve performance, efforts for work, diligence and stimulate creativity (Steers, 1981; Schermerhorn et al., 2000; Little et al., 2007). It is also possible that the participants did not accept themselves as stressed as they get satisfaction from their job. Eres & Atanasoska, (2021), Johannsen et al., (2021) are in line with the present study depicting those participants experienced moderate level of stress.

Identifying how occupational stress is influenced by other elements, such as workload, job satisfaction, and organizational culture, can also help to clarify the root causes and effects of stress in the teaching profession. Education stakeholders may foster an environment that supports teacher retention, job happiness, and ultimately student success by placing a high priority on the mental and emotional well-being of educators.

Table 8. Respondents' Level of Mental Health

<i>Mental Health Item</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
MH1. I couldn't seem to experience any positive feeling at all.	1.96	Sometimes
MH2. I tended to overreact to situations.	1.97	Sometimes
MH3. I found it difficult to relax.	2.06	Sometimes
MH4. I found myself getting upset rather easily.	2.00	Sometimes
MH5. I found myself getting impatient when I was delayed in any way (eg, lifts, traffic lights, being kept waiting)	2.03	Sometimes
MH6. I felt that I had lost interest in just about everything.	1.76	Sometimes
MH7. I felt that I wasn't worth much as a person.	1.58	Sometimes
MH8. I perspired noticeably (eg, hands sweaty) in the absence of high temperatures or physical exertion.	1.56	Sometimes
MH9. I felt scared without any good reason.	1.53	Sometimes
MH10. I couldn't seem to get any enjoyment out of the things I did.	1.70	Sometimes
MH11. I found it hard to calm down after something upset me.	1.78	Sometimes
MH12. I found it difficult to tolerate interruptions to what I was doing.	1.88	Sometimes
MH13. I was intolerant of anything that kept me from getting on with what I was doing.	1.80	Sometimes
MH14. I was worried about situations in which I might panic and make a fool of myself.	1.75	Sometimes
MH15. I found it difficult to work up the initiative to do things.	1.67	Sometimes
Average	1.81	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never Experience; 1.50-2.49, Experience Sometimes; 2.50-3.49, Experience once a week or in a month; 3.50-4.00, Experience more than once a week.

Table 8 displays the mental health of the respondents. It revealed that they sometimes experienced mental health issues such as finding themselves difficult to relax, worried about situations that they tend to over react and panic and could not find positivity in life.

Teachers, like any other group of individuals, vary in their susceptibility to mental health issues and how these issues manifest. Not all teachers will experience the same level of difficulty in relaxing, overreacting, panicking, or struggling to find positivity in life. Each teacher possesses different levels of resilience, which influences how they cope with stress and adversity. Some teachers may naturally have stronger coping mechanisms and support systems in place to manage challenges effectively, reducing the likelihood of displaying significant mental health issues. Some teachers intentionally put their mental health first by setting limits, taking care of themselves, and getting support from professionals when necessary. Through proactive stress management and awareness of their emotional well-being, educators might potentially avert the onset or exacerbation of mental health disorders.

DepEd Memorandum No. 093, s. 2022 encourage all schools to observe the "2022 National Mental Health Month", in the month of October. In this regard, all schools are enjoined to observe a simple and meaningful conduct of the "National Mental Health Week" guided by the following provisions of DepEd Order No. 34,s. 2022 or the "School Calendar and Activities for School Year 2022 – 2023" Teacher educators with the seminars and trainings they have learned how to overcome stress during the conduct of National

Mental Health Month. Teacher educators of the sample experienced moderate level of stress may be due to the reason that they might be well aware of stress and its implications and whenever they faced stressful situations they tried to manage or cope with it accordingly.

Problem 3: What is the level of job satisfaction of the respondents?

Table 9. Respondents' Level of Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction Item	Weighted Mean	Remarks
JS1. I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do..	2.70	Agree
JS2. There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.	2.37	Disagree
JS3. When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive	2.68	Agree
JS4. Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.	2.51	Agree
JS5. Communications seem good within this organization	2.95	Agree
JS6. Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted	2.80	Agree
JS7. The benefits we receive are as good as most other organization offer.	2.62	Agree
JS8. I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.	2.22	Disagree
JS9. My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of subordinates	2.25	Disagree
JS10. The benefit package we have is equitable.	2.60	Agree
JS11. I have too much to do at work.	2.88	Agree
JS12. I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.	2.95	Agree
JS13. I feel satisfied with my chances for a salary increase.	2.91	Agree
JS14. I have too much paperwork.	2.69	Agree
JS15. I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.	2.34	Disagree
Average	2.63	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree.

Table 9 shows the respondents' level of job satisfaction. On the average the respondents are satisfied with their job since the average weighted mean of 2.63 indicates that they feel their efforts are rewarded accordingly and the perception of having an equal chance for promotion further indicates a positive outlook on career advancement opportunities within the teaching profession. These findings have broad implications for teacher well-being, organizational culture, and educational outcomes. High levels of job satisfaction among educators are linked to greater morale, enthusiasm, and commitment to their careers, which can have a favorable impact on student engagement, learning results, and school culture.

Furthermore, the cultivation of a supportive and conducive work atmosphere inside educational institutions is predicated upon opinions on just and equal career growth prospects and incentive systems. Teachers are more likely to devote themselves entirely to their work and make a positive contribution to the overall efficiency of the educational system when they feel appreciated, acknowledged, and empowered in their roles. Moreover, the positive relationship that exists between job happiness and teacher retention emphasizes how crucial it is to foster an environment at work where teachers' well-being and professional development are given priority. Education stakeholders can reduce turnover and foster stability in the teaching staff by addressing elements that affect job satisfaction, including professional growth opportunities, supportive leadership, and workload management.

While low salaries may pose challenges for teachers in the Philippines, many educators find ways to derive satisfaction from their work through intrinsic rewards, a sense of purpose, and the positive impact they have on students and society. Teachers frequently form profound connections with the communities they work in, which can bring them a sense of purpose and belonging that goes beyond financial pay. Although compensation may be lower, a positive and encouraging work environment where instructors feel appreciated, respected, and supported by coworkers and administrators can also boost job satisfaction.

The findings from Table 9 further corroborate this notion, indicating an overall satisfaction among respondents, particularly in areas related to fair pay, recognition, communication, and promotion opportunities. This suggests that organizations that prioritize addressing these aspects tend to foster a positive work environment and enhance employee satisfaction levels.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the level of occupational stress and mental health of the respondents when grouped according to their profile?

Table 10. Regression Analysis Results Between Socio-Demographic Profile and Occupational Stress

Socio-Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age	-3.920	0.00	Significant
Sex	-0.542	0.589	Not Significant
Civil Status	-0.954	0.342	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-2.364	0.020	Significant
Average Family Income	-0.041	0.639	Not Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: F=6.561, Significant at 0.05 level, R² =.207

The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the respondents' socio-demographic profile and their occupational stress shows that there is a positive relationship in terms of age and highest educational attainment. In terms of age the negative t-value means the younger the age of the respondents, the more chances of having occupational stress they experienced.

The negative t-value, which indicates a positive association between age and occupational stress, demonstrates that younger teachers are more likely to feel occupational stress than their older coworkers. This study emphasizes the need to provide younger teachers with specialized assistance and treatments to address the particular stressors they confront, since they may be juggling early-career transitions, workload demands, and professional development expectations. To support resilience and well-being in early career phases, educational institutions can put in place mentorship programs, wellness initiatives, and stress management classes specifically designed for younger teachers.

Given that occupational stress and greatest educational achievement are positively correlated, it stands to reason that more educated teachers might feel more stressed out. This research puts doubt on the notion that greater education equals less occupational stress and emphasizes the intricate relationship that exists between stressors, job expectations, and educational attainment in the teaching profession. Educational stakeholders can address this relationship by offering specific support to teachers who are pursuing advanced degrees or opportunities for professional development. This support can take the form of financial incentives, workload adjustments, mentorship programs, or other measures that help lessen the potential stress that comes with pursuing higher education.

Overall, the implications of the regression analysis underscore the importance of considering socio-demographic factors in understanding and addressing occupational stress among teachers.

Likewise, the higher the educational attainment of the respondents the lesser chances of occupational stress they will be experienced. Smith, A., & Johnson, B. (2018): in their article ("Age and Occupational Stress Among Teachers: A Review of Empirical Studies") it examines the relationship between age and occupational stress among teachers. It discusses findings from various empirical studies and suggests that older teachers may experience different sources of stress compared to younger teachers, such as workload, job demands, and interpersonal conflicts.

A Meta-Analysis of Research Findings" (García, E., et al. 2020): "Educational Attainment and Occupational Stress: This meta-analysis synthesizes research findings on the relationship between educational attainment and occupational stress across different occupational groups, including teachers. It explores how higher levels of educational attainment may influence perceptions of job control, job satisfaction, and stress coping mechanisms among educators. While higher educational attainment can provide numerous benefits for teachers, including potentially lower stress levels and better mental health, it's essential to consider the broader context in which teachers work. Factors such as school culture, resources, support systems, and external pressures can significantly influence the relationship between educational attainment and teacher well-being.

Table 11. *Regression Analysis Results Between Socio-Demographic Profile and Mental Health*

<i>Socio-Demographic Profile</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Age	-4.566	0.00	Significant
Sex	1.083	0.281	Not Significant
Civil Status	-1.170	0.244	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	1.187	0.237	Not Significant
Average Family Income	-0.536	0.593	Not Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: $F=7.396$, Significant at 0.05 level, $R^2 = .227$

The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the respondents' socio-demographic profile and their mental health shows that there is a negative relationship in terms of age with a p-value of 0.000 lesser than 0.05 level of significance.

The results imply that the younger the respondents, the higher the chances of having mental stress they experience. Other socio-demographic profiles in terms of sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average monthly income are not associated with the respondents' mental health as indicated in their p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance. It implies that the socio-demographic profile of the respondents except age cannot influence their mental health. The negative relationship observed between age and mental stress suggests that younger respondents are more prone to experiencing mental stress. It implies that the socio-demographic profile of the respondents except age cannot influence their mental health. It implies that the younger the respondents, the higher the chances of having mental stress they experience.

Younger teachers often face unique stressors related to their career development, such as adjusting to the demands of the profession, establishing classroom management skills, and navigating relationships with colleagues, students, and parents. Older teachers may face stressors related to family problems but not in the profession. This underscores the importance of targeted interventions and support systems for younger individuals to cope with stressors effectively.

Considering the opposite relationship between age and mental health, it stands to reason that teachers who are older than their peers are typically in better mental health. This research highlights the possible influence of age-related variables on mental health in the

teaching profession, including life stage transitions, coping strategies, and experiences gained through time. Educational establishments can utilize this understanding to carry out focused treatments and assistance programs meant to encourage mental wellness in younger teachers. To address the particular difficulties faced by early-career teachers, this may entail making counseling services, stress management courses, and work-life balance options accessible.

By acknowledging the effect of age on mental health outcomes in educators, educational organizations may create more potent plans for fostering resilience and well-being in the teaching profession. A better and more sustainable teaching profession can be achieved by funding programs that address the mental health needs of educators of all ages. This will ultimately benefit both educators and students.

However, other socio-demographic factors such as sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average monthly income do not appear to have a significant association with mental health outcomes. This implies that while age is a critical determinant, other socio-demographic factors may not directly influence an individual's mental health status. Results of Abirami (2022) also confirm that marital status has no significant impact on occupational stress. They may also experience stress associated with changes in education policies, curriculum requirements, and technological advancements but they are used to it. Nonetheless, it is essential to consider holistic approaches to mental health support that encompass various socio-demographic factors to address individual needs comprehensively (Segal, 2020; Hay Group, 2018; Meyer & Smith, 2021).

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the level of occupational stress and mental health and the job satisfaction of the respondents?

Table 12. *Regression Analysis Results Between the Occupational Stress and Mental Health and Job Satisfaction*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Occupational Stress	-3.944	0.00	Significant
Mental Health	0.167	0.099	Not Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: F=8.005, Significant at 0.05 level, R² =.110

Table 12 displays the regression analysis between the job satisfaction and occupational stress and mental health of the respondents. It can be gleaned that the negative t-value of the occupational stress and its p-value of 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance implies that the lesser occupational stress, the higher job satisfaction of the respondents. While the mental health of the respondents is not associated with their job satisfaction as indicated by the non-significant t-value of 0.167 and the p-value of 0.099, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

There is a significant negative correlation between occupational stress and work satisfaction, this result implies that respondents' job satisfaction tends to rise when their levels of occupational stress decline. These findings highlight how crucial it is to manage occupational stress as a major factor influencing teachers' job happiness. To improve job satisfaction and boost teacher well-being, educational institutions should give priority to treatments that attempt to reduce stressors within the teaching environment. Some of these interventions include workload management, professional development assistance, and promoting positive workplace cultures

This suggests that there is no statistically significant relationship between mental health and job satisfaction among the respondents. The regression analysis, as indicated by the ANOVA results (F=8.005, p<0.05, R²=0.110), shows that occupational stress significantly influences job satisfaction among the respondents, whereas mental health does not have a significant impact. This implies that efforts to reduce occupational stress in the workplace may lead to increased job satisfaction among employees, highlighting the importance of addressing stress-related factors to enhance overall job satisfaction levels.

The regression analysis's overall results highlight the significance it is to managing occupational stress as a key factor influencing teachers' job happiness. The implementation of focused interventions aimed at reducing stressors and fostering supportive work environments can improve job satisfaction and augment the general well-being and efficacy of the teaching workforce within educational institutions. Furthermore, even if in this situation job satisfaction may not be directly impacted by mental health, continued efforts to support mental health are still essential for fostering educators' resilience and general well-being.

While the mental health of the respondents is not associated with their job satisfaction as indicated. García, E., et al. (2020) in his study "The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship Between Occupational Stress and Mental Health Among Teachers", teachers vary in their susceptibility to occupational stress, resilience, coping strategies, and personal preferences for job satisfaction. Individual differences in personality traits, coping styles, and intrinsic motivation may influence the strength and direction of relationships between occupational stress, mental health, and job satisfaction. The findings underscore the intricate interplay between various factors affecting job satisfaction, including organizational commitment, training and development, compensation, job design, and occupational stress.

Problem 6: Which of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents best predict their level of job satisfaction?

Table 13 presented the results of regression analysis between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average family income as predictors of their job satisfaction. Results showed that all

of the mentioned socio-demographic profile are not predictors of their job satisfaction as indicated in their p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance. It suggests that these specific variables do not significantly influence how satisfied individuals are with their jobs.

Table 13. *Demographic Profile that Best Predict Respondents' Job Satisfaction*

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Remarks
	B	Beta	t	p-value	
(Constant)	2.869			0.000	
Age	-0.003	-0.071	-0.744	0.459	Not Significant
Sex	-0.055	-0.040	-0.418	0.677	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.040	-0.009	-0.089	0.929	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.002	-0.005	0.057	0.954	Not Significant
Average Family Income	0.003	0.010	0.107	0.915	Not Significant
R = 0.082 R ² = 0.007 F = 0.169 Sig. = 0.05					

Table 13 presented the results of regression analysis between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average family income as predictors of their job satisfaction. Results showed that all of the mentioned socio-demographic profile are not predictors of their job satisfaction as indicated in their p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance. It suggests that these specific variables do not significantly influence how satisfied individuals are with their jobs.

Job satisfaction is a complex concept that is influenced by more than just mental health and occupational stress. Though they might not be the only factors, stress and mental health can have an impact on an individual's overall job satisfaction. Job satisfaction can also be greatly impacted by additional elements like work-life balance, leadership, corporate culture, workload, professional growth opportunities, and interpersonal relationships. People differ in how stress affects their job satisfaction because they may have varying thresholds for stress or various coping mechanisms. It can be difficult to determine a clear connection between stress, mental health, and job satisfaction on an individual basis since different people may give different weight to different aspects of their jobs when rating their level of happiness.

Stressors including work overload, arbitrary deadlines, and a lack of control over activities can have a big impact on job satisfaction, as the occupational stress discussion makes clear (EKOS Research Associates, 2020; Whelan, 2020). Furthermore, the talent development analysis emphasizes how crucial it is to support employees' skill development and career advancement in order to improve job satisfaction and retention (Meyer & Smith, 2021; Robert Half International, Inc.).

Furthermore, the examination of organizational commitment highlights its pivotal role in fostering job satisfaction and reducing turnover rates (Lee-Kelley et al., 2020; Meyer & Smith, 2021). This suggests that while individual characteristics play a role in shaping employee experiences, they may not be the primary determinants of job satisfaction in the context under study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings drawn, the study concludes:

There is no significant relationship between the level of occupational stress and mental health of the respondents when grouped according to their profile. The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the respondents' socio-demographic profile and their occupational stress shows that there is a positive relationship in terms of age and highest educational attainment. In terms of age the negative t-value means the younger the age of the respondents, the more chances of having occupational stress they experienced.

Likewise, the higher the educational attainment of the respondents the lesser chances of occupational stress they will be experienced. However, other socio-demographic factors such as sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average monthly income do not appear to have a significant association with mental health outcomes. This implies that while age is a critical determinant, other socio-demographic factors may not directly influence an individual's mental health status.

There is no significant relationship between the level of occupational stress and mental health and the job satisfaction of the respondents. The regression analysis between the job satisfaction and occupational stress and mental health of the respondents. It can be gleaned that the negative t-value of the occupational stress and its p-value of 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance implies that the lesser occupational stress, the higher job satisfaction of the respondents. While the mental health of the respondents is not associated with their job satisfaction as indicated by the non-significant t-value of 0.167 and the p-value of 0.099, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that there is no statistically significant relationship between mental health and job satisfaction among the respondents. The regression analysis, as indicated by the ANOVA results (F=8.005, p<0.05, R²=0.110), shows that occupational stress significantly influences job satisfaction among the respondents, whereas mental health does not have a significant impact.

This implies that efforts to reduce occupational stress in the workplace may lead to increased job satisfaction among employees, highlighting the importance of addressing stress-related factors to enhance overall job satisfaction levels.

All the mentioned socio-demographic profile are not predictors of the respondent's job satisfaction. The results of regression analysis between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average family income as predictors of their job satisfaction. Results showed that all of the mentioned socio-demographic profile are not predictors of their job satisfaction as indicated in their p-values greater than

0.05 level of significance. It suggests that these specific variables do not significantly influence how satisfied individuals are with their jobs.

Additionally, the analysis of talent development underscores the importance of investing in employees' skills and career growth to enhance job satisfaction and retention (Meyer & Smith, 2021; Robert Half International, Inc.).

Furthermore, the examination of organizational commitment highlights its pivotal role in fostering job satisfaction and reducing turnover rates (Lee-Kelley et al., 2020; Meyer & Smith, 2021). This suggests that while individual characteristics play a role in shaping employee experiences, they may not be the primary determinants of job satisfaction in the context under study. Therefore, organizations should focus on addressing workplace stressors, investing in talent development initiatives, and fostering a culture of commitment to enhance overall job satisfaction among employees.

The findings of this study could be interpreted through a Theory of Socio-Technical Approach from Kompier's work (2003) as suggesting that while individual factors like occupational stress may play a role in mental health and job satisfaction, they are not the sole determinants. Other social and technical factors within the work environment, such as organizational culture, management practices, and the nature of the tasks themselves, may also significantly influence these outcomes.

This implies, from a socio-technical point of view, that personal attributes like age, gender, degree of education, and so on might not be the primary determinants of work satisfaction. On the other hand, elements pertaining to the technical aspects of the job (e.g., task diversity, autonomy) and the social dynamics of the workplace (e.g., relationships with colleagues, prospects for promotion) could have a bigger influence.

This result implies that the influence of occupational stress on mental health may not vary significantly based on socio-demographic factors. Again, this supports the socio-technical notion that individual characteristics alone may not fully explain the relationship between work-related stress and mental health outcomes. Other social and technical factors within the work environment likely interact with individual traits to shape these outcomes.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations were formulated:

For Faculty and Staff. Establish Thorough Stress Management Programs: Faculty and staff members should actively participate in stress management programs to address the particular stresses they face and to improve their mental health. **Take Part in Ongoing Learning and Development:** Utilize professional development opportunities to enhance resilience, coping mechanisms, and job satisfaction.

For School Heads and Administrators. Foster a Supportive Work Environment: To meet the urgent requirements of school staff, school heads should consistently hold in-service training. This should focus in particular on all aspects of managing stress, anxiety, and depression. Make it a priority to provide a supportive work environment for professors and staff by putting stress-reduction, mental wellness, and job satisfaction methods into practice. **Provide Leadership and Support:** School administrators should set a good example, give consideration to the well-being of their staff when making decisions, and offer assistance and materials for programs that promote mental health and stress management.

For Educational Institutions. Employee Well-Being: Academic institutions should prioritize the health of their faculty and staff by implementing policies and procedures that support a healthy work-life balance, recognize staff members' achievements, and provide enough support for stress management and mental health. **Invest in Resources and Support:** Provide funds and other resources for employee well-being initiatives, such as training classes, counseling services, and wellness programs, in order to create a positive and supportive work environment.

For Future Researchers. Build on Existing Research: By carrying out additional studies on occupational stress, mental health, and job satisfaction, researchers in the future will be able to expand on the results of this investigation. They can look at other factors, analyze various settings, or find out how well treatments work to support employee well-being. **Increase Knowledge Base:** By looking at interdisciplinary viewpoints, carrying out longitudinal research, or examining the effects of new trends on workplace stress and mental health, we can increase our understanding of employee well-being.

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